

Pathogen prescription predicament: Evaluating the appropriateness of antibiotic regimens for *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*

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Abstract

Objectives: The primary objective of this study was to assess the suitability of treatment guidelines for selected critical and high priority organisms recognized by the World Health Organization (WHO), namely *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. A secondary aim was to evaluate the pattern of Carbapenem resistance in *A baumannii* and *P aeruginosa*, as well as Methicillin resistance in *S aureus*.

Methods: The Pfizer-Atlas bacterial dataset was utilized with R version 4.3.1 being used for exploratory data analysis. Subgroup analyses were performed using tidyr to examine different antibiotics and countries with resistance trend being presented in chart and maps respectively. A review of preferred regimens for treatment of the three organisms from the past decade was conducted. These recommended antibiotics were compared with resistant isolates (Meropenem for *A baumannii* and *P aeruginosa*, Oxacillin for *S aureus*) to calculate odds ratios of cross resistance.

Results: *Acinetobacter baumannii*: Analysis of the 38,036 isolates revealed 55.6% being resistant to at least one Carbapenem. Colistin and Minocycline showed resistance levels below 10% in 2021, aligning with previous preferred regimens. In *A baumannii*, the odds ratio for cross resistance with meropenem was highest for Piperacillin tazobactam (OR: 658.4, 95% CI: 614.5-723.6) and lowest for Colistin (OR: 0.001, 95% CI: 0.0004-0.0014).

Pseudomonas aeruginosa: Among 94,460 isolates, 25.3% were resistant to one or more carbapenem. Among isolates with existing Meropenem resistance, Colistin showed the lowest odds of cross resistance (OR 0.009, 95% CI [0.008-0.01]). Similarly Amikacin, Imipenem, Ceftazidime avibactam and Doripenem had odds ratios of less than 1. Among the selected antibiotics, only Piperacillin tazobactam had increased risk of cross resistance with Meropenem (Odds Ratio = 2.54, 95% CI [2.41, 2.70])

Staphylococcus aureus: Analysis of 95,906 isolates showed that 68.4% had the Methicillin Resistant phenotype. In the outpatient setting, Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) strains which were resistant to Oxacillin showed a significant resistance to Clindamycin (25%) while Linezolid, Tigecycline, Clindamycin, Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, and Minocycline had resistance rates under 5%. In the inpatient setting, Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) strains exhibited higher cross resistance between Oxacillin and Clindamycin (40%) with only intermediate resistance isolates for Vancomycin(5), Daptomycin(88) and Tigecycline(418).

Conclusion: This study provides valuable insights into the antibiotic resistance patterns of *A. baumannii*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The findings suggest that previously suggested empiric regimens in the above organisms may not be appropriate based on the current trends. These findings contribute to evidence-based approach for selecting antibiotics and combating antimicrobial resistance, aiding individuals, organizations, and countries in developing guidelines for effective treatment.

Objectives

The primary objective of this study was to assess the suitability of treatment guidelines for selected priority/critical organisms recognized by the World Health Organization (WHO), namely *A. baumannii*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S aureus*. A secondary aim was to evaluate the pattern of Carbapenem resistance in *A. baumannii* and *P. aeruginosa*, as well as Methicillin resistance in *S aureus*.

Methodology

The Pfizer-Atlas bacterial dataset was used. The dataset had the MIC values and the resistance interpretation. We utilized R version 4.3.1 to perform data cleaning and exploratory data analysis. Some of the R libraries used were tidyverse, SmartEDA and forecast. Age was excluded from further analysis due to the wide age bands used in the original dataset. We wrangled the data using tidyr to perform sub group analysis of different antibiotics and countries. The MRSA data was further sub grouped into outpatient and inpatient isolates. We did a review of the commonly preferred regimens in the past decade. These recommended antibiotics were then compared with resistant isolates (Meropenem for *A baumannii* and *P aeruginosa*, Oxacillin for *S aureus*) to calculate odds ratios of cross resistance with these recommended antibiotics.

Results

Acinetobacter baumannii

A total of 38,036 isolates with *A baumannii* were present with 21,139(55.6%) being resistant to at least one carbapenem. The country with the highest number of **Carbapenem resistant** isolates was United States with 10.8%. Regarding gender distribution, females comprised approximately 36.6% of this group, while the largest proportion fell in the 19 to 64 year category (51%). 91.4% of the **Carbapenem resistant** isolates were from the inpatient setting with the most common specialty being general medical at 31.7%. In terms of the sample source Sputum (16.7%) and Blood (15.6%) samples constituted the majority, followed by Wound (13.1%), Urine (9.5%) and Endotracheal aspirate (8.1%).

Figure 1: Count and percentage of Meropenem resistant *A. Baumannii* isolates in 2004, 2010 and 2020

From 2004 to 2021, the resistance pattern of all *A. Baumannii* isolates to various antibiotics was as follows. Amikacin resistance increased gradually from 17% in 2004 to 60% in 2021. Imipenem and meropenem showed relatively high resistance rates, ranging from 16% to 71%. Minocycline exhibited resistance rates between 3% and 11%. Colistin remained effective with resistance rates below 20% in most years.

Figure 2: Trend of *A. baumannii* antibiotic resistance percentage from 2004 to 2021

In 2021, only Colistin and Minocycline had resistance levels of less than 10% with the previous preferred regimens having resistance levels of over 50%. In *A. baumannii*, the odds ratio for cross resistance with Meropenem was significantly higher for Amikacin (OR: 7.3, 95% CI: 6.9-7.6) and Piperacillin tazobactam (OR: 658.4, 95% CI: 614.5-723.6). Conversely, Colistin (OR: 0.001, 95% CI: 0.0004-0.0014) and Doripenem (OR: 0.02, 95% CI: 0.01-0.03) had significantly lower odds of cross resistance with Meropenem.

Table 1: Cross resistance of different antibiotics with meropenem in *A. baumannii* isolates (n=20,336)

Antibiotic	Resistance(Count)	Resistance(Percentage)	Odds Ratio	95% Confidence Interval
Amikacin	14,832	72.90%	7.3	[6.9, 7.6]
Ampicillin sulbactam	6,347	31.20%	0.21	[0.2, 0.3]
Colistin	533	2.60%	0.001	[0.0004, 0.0014]
Doripenem	2,420	11.90%	0.02	[0.01, 0.03]
Imipenem	10,845	53.30%	1.3	[1.2, 1.4]
Minocycline	989	4.90%	0.001	[0.0005, 0.0015]
Piperacillin tazobactam	19,574	96.30%	658.4	[614.5, 723.6]

Pseudomonas aeruginosa

There were 94,460 isolates with *P. aeruginosa* with 25.3% of them being resistant to one or more carbapenem. The number of isolates from males was 62.2% while from females was 37.8%. The most occurring age groups was the 19 to 64 group (44.3%) with the highest specialty being general medicine (35.3%). The trend of all *P. aeruginosa* isolates was as follows. Meropenem resistance ranged from 18% to 30%. Piperacillin-tazobactam resistance remained consistently moderate, ranging from 15% to 28%. Aztreonam and ceftazidime-avibactam exhibited relatively low resistance rates, with fluctuations below 10%. Doripenem and colistin remained effective with resistance rates below 20% in most years.

Figure 3: Trend of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* resistance percentage from 2004 to 2021

Among isolates with existing Meropenem resistance, Colistin showed the lowest odds of cross resistance (OR 0.009, 95% CI [0.008-0.01]). Similarly, Amikacin, Imipenem, Ceftazidime avibactam and Doripenem had odds ratios of less than 1. Among the selected antibiotics, only Piperacillin tazobactam had increased risk of cross resistance with meropenem (Odds Ratio = 2.54, 95% CI [2.41, 2.70]).

Table 2: Cross resistance of different antibiotics with meropenem in *P. aeruginosa* isolates (n=18,555)

Antibiotic	Resistance (Count)	Resistance (Percentage)	Odds Ratio	95% Confidence Interval
Amikacin	4,811	26%	0.53	[0.5, 0.6]
Ceftazidime avibactam	4,115	22%	0.40	[0.37, 0.43]
Colistin	165	1%	0.009	[0.008, 0.01]
Doripenem	3,548	19%	0.31	[0.29, 0.33]
Imipenem	4,170	22%	0.41	[0.38, 0.44]
Piperacillin tazobactam	10,837	58%	2.54	[2.41, 2.70]

Staphylococcus aureus

There were 95,906 isolates of *S aureus*. In terms of phenotype, MSSA accounted for 55.5% and MRSA accounted for 44.5%.

In terms of the total *S Aureus* isolates, the antibiotic trend over time was as follows. Clindamycin resistance started at 0% in 2004, reached a peak of 25% in 2013, and then decreased to 11% in 2019. Daptomycin resistance remained consistently low at 0% from 2004 to 2014 and increased to 37% in 2021. Linezolid resistance showed a fluctuating pattern, with a peak of 4% in 2012 and 2013, but it remained below 1% in other years. Minocycline resistance started at 0% and gradually increased to 30% by 2019. Finally, vancomycin resistance remained consistently low at 0% throughout the entire period analyzed.

Figure 4: Trend of *Staphylococcus aureus* resistance percentage from 2004 to 2021

Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

The top three countries reporting MRSA isolates were United States with 20.99%, Spain with 5.81%, and Italy with 5.17%. The sex distribution was 59.3% male and 40.7% female. The two highest age groups were the 19 to 64 group (48.3%) and the 65 to 84 group (32.1%). Where indicated, 14% of the MRSA isolates were documented from the outpatient setting while 86% were from the in-patient. The highest specialties encountering *P aeruginosa* were Medicine general (42.3%) and Surgery general (16.3%). The top three sources of MRSA isolates based on the given data were wound (27.08%), blood (12.80%), and sputum (14.34%).

Figure 1: Count and percentage of Meropenem resistant *A. baumannii* isolates in 2004, 2010 and 2020

In the outpatient setting, Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) strains which were resistant to Oxacillin showed a significant resistance to Clindamycin (25%). Linezolid, Tigecycline, Clindamycin, Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, and Minocycline had resistance rates under 5 %.

Table 3: Cross resistance of different *S. aureus* antibiotics with oxacillin in *S. aureus* in the outpatient setting (n=3,674)

MRSA-OutPatient	Clindamycin	Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole	Minocycline	Linezolid	Tigecycline*
Count	905	101	112	1	0
Percentage	25%	3%	3%	0%	0%

*Intermediate isolates Tigecycline(38)

In the inpatient setting, Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) strains exhibited moderate cross resistance between Oxacillin and Clindamycin. There were no resistant isolates, just intermediate resistant isolates, in Vancomycin(5), Daptomycin(88) and Tigecycline(418),

Table 4: Cross resistance of different *S. aureus* antibiotics with oxacillin in *S. aureus* in the inpatient setting (n=30,304)

MRSA-In Patient	Vancomycin*	Linezolid	Daptomycin*	Clindamycin	Tigecycline*
Count	0	9	0	12207	0
Percentage	0%	0%	0%	40%	0%

*Intermediate isolates Vancomycin(5), Daptomycin(88), Tigecycline(418)

Impact

This study was able to identify the prevalence of the 3 organisms and the proportion of Carbapenem resistance in *A. baumannii* and *P. aeruginosa* and Methicillin resistance in *S. aureus*. These organisms are of global importance as per the World Health Organisation. The most common source of *A. baumannii* was sputum, however as per Bartal et al. (2022), when *A. baumannii* is isolated from a non-sterile site, it probably represents colonization hence clear signs of infection must be established. More corroboration with clinical information is needed to distinguish colonization from infection.

Carbapenems, aminoglycosides, betalactamase inhibitors, tetracyclines, polymyxins and glycolcyclines have all been recommended for *A. baumannii* infection in the last decade (Doi et al., 2009). In 2021, only Colistin and Minocycline had resistance levels of less than 10% with the previous preferred regimens having resistance levels of over 50%. Our findings demonstrate that these remain the viable options in carbapenem resistant *A. baumannii* infection.

Our findings on *P. aeruginosa* trends show relatively lower resistance percentages across Carbapenems which would be an area of possible research. Karruli et al. (2023) suggested using ceftolozane-tazobactam or ceftazidime-avibactam as empirical treatment for suspected *P. aeruginosa* and this is corroborated by our findings which show that both have sub 10% resistance levels.

For MRSA in the outpatient setting, oral antibiotic options include clindamycin, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, minocycline or linezolid. In the inpatient, intravenous vancomycin, linezolid, daptomycin and clindamycin have been recommended. Of these clindamycin is showing moderate levels of resistance suggesting that it should not be considered for the empiric treatment of MRSA in the both settings.

The limitations of the Pfizer/Atlas was the paucity of data in the developing world leading to underrepresentation of the burden of these organisms in these regions. Also the preprocessing of data e.g. Age into categories limited the subgroup analysis.

While these findings are not immediately generalizable to the entire health system, they provide useful sentinel information regarding emerging trends in these WHO priority and critical organisms. These findings can help individuals, organizations and countries develop an evidenced based approach to antibiotic choices put in guidelines. These guidelines can then be updated depending on the current trends in resistance. This will go a long way in combating antimicrobial resistance.

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